

LABEL2 ENABLE

Project acronym: Label2Enable

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EU mHealth label for a single market that enables
patients, citizens, health professionals, systems and
authorities to benefit from a healthy supply of useful apps

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Abstract

This document details the development of the Label2Enable website and further plans for its update and maintenance throughout the project. It also presents a slide deck that can be used mainly by project partners to present the project and its goals. Finally, a brochure has been developed for dissemination purposes and reported in this document.

Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a first in a series of reports focusing on the promotion of the Label2Enable project, which broadly includes the development of a promotion action plan, continuous dissemination and communication of project activities and results, and engagement and growth of the stakeholder community that is engaged in the topics that Label2Enable addresses. The document features three prioritised dissemination and communication means: a project website, a generic slide deck, and a project brochure.

The project website was launched on 7 September 2022. It aims to raise awareness about Label2Enable's progress and results and act as an information platform for mHealth stakeholders wishing to know more about the project. The website has an open and easy to use interface and a robust build, according to the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) AA standards. The website provides information about the project, about CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2, and relevant EU policies. It features a news and events section, as well as an engagement menu, encouraging interactions with external audiences. It also offers a subscription form used to grow the project community and enable the project to send targeted updates in the future. The website is being continuously improved and developed further, aiming to include new elements such as a results section to feature emerging project outcomes.

A project presentation slide deck has been elaborated in order to enable project partners to present key project facts in a uniform way at various events and communication opportunities. The slide deck contains the most important information on Label2Enable and CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2, mirroring the content on the website. The slide deck prominently refers to the website and the project's social media accounts, encouraging following and newsletter sign-up.

A project brochure has been prepared, aiming at complementing the website content and directing community traffic to the page, as well as to the project's social media. The brochure is aimed to be disseminated on the website and on social media. Ad hoc printed versions can be created for offline communication, especially during relevant events. It provides key information in one place – defining the problem space the project is addressing, positioning of the project within the context of key EU policy developments, explaining the principles of CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2:2021, its quality label and associated report, presenting a visual of the label elements, elaborating the main stakeholders the project is targeting, and giving a high-level overview of key project activities, grouped in the pillars trust, use and adoption.

A comprehensive dissemination and communication structure has been set up with a virtual Communication Office Team comprising representatives of all project partners. The members meet regularly to coordinate efforts, identify communication and dissemination opportunities and take stock of completed dissemination activities. Future plans and achievements will be reported in the following deliverables (D6.2, D6.3).

1 Introduction

This document is a first in a series of reports focusing on the promotion of the Label2Enable project, which broadly includes the development of a promotion action plan, continuous dissemination and communication of project activities and results, and engagement and growth of the stakeholder community that is engaged in the topics that Label2Enable addresses.

The document focuses on three main priority promotional activities that have been performed in the first months of the project:

1. Setting up a project website
2. Developing a slide deck for use by project partners
3. Developing a project brochure

2 Project website

This section describes the outline, management and genesis of the project website, located at www.label2enable.eu.

The Figure below shows the project website's landing page on launch day (7 September 2022).

Figure 1. Label2Enable website (September 2022)

2.1 Website objectives and target audience

The website aims to raise awareness about Label2Enable's progress and results and act as an information platform for mHealth stakeholders wishing to know more about the project. The target audience spans all stakeholders the label is directed at:

- Patients, citizens and carers;
- Health care professionals;
- Healthcare and reimbursement authorities (incl. health technology assessment bodies and insurers);
- App manufacturers;
- App checkers/ certification bodies;
- App stores and libraries.

In addition, the website also aims at reaching a broader target audience with indirect links to mHealth, such as:

- Other digital health EU projects;
- Research organisations active in digital health;
- Broader industry (e.g., pharma, non-mHealth medical technology).

2.2 Main organisations involved

Several entities involved in the project conceptualise, design, develop, and maintain the project website:

- LUMC as project coordinator provides overall guidance on alignment of the website with the essence of the project
- A graphic design studio – Bureau OS¹ – subcontracted by LUMC is responsible for the visual design and layout of the website and other key project documents targeting the wider public (brochure, PowerPoint presentation).
- A web development agency – Qabana² – subcontracted by LUMC is responsible for the technical setup of the website and technical support in maintenance and further development during the project.
- EMPIRICA as WP6 lead is responsible for populating the website with content and for coordinating consortium partners' input to and planning of promotional activities and results, which are communicated and disseminated, among other channels, through the website.

2.3 Design choices and considerations

Label2Enable aims to feature a website with an open and easy to use interface and robust build.

The design of the website is inspired by the CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2 label and Label2Enable logo. Both have been developed by Bureau OS prior to the project start. Just as the CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2 sets clear guidance for app manufacturers on usability and accessibility of apps, the project strives to provide an easy-to-use website which meets the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG)³ AA standards. This applies both to the use of colours as well as overall navigation and user experience.

In addition, the project will seek regular feedback from user representatives who are engaged through different project activities, including through patients, citizens and carers convened via an advisory group established under Task 4.1 and led by partner EPF, and nurses and physicians convened via an advisory group established under Task 5.1 led by partner LSM.

In terms of colour palette, the website uses colours which offer high contrast and conform to the WCAG AA level:

¹ <https://www.bureauos.design/>

² <https://qabana.nl/>

³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Web_Content_Accessibility_Guidelines

2.4 Technical implementation

The website is available under the domain name www.label2enable.eu which the consortium had already reserved during the project's proposal phase. The domain is hosted by EMPIRICA.

Jointly with WP6 lead EMPIRICA, coordinator LUMC decided to use the Content Management System Statamic⁴ for the project website. Statamic offers a complete suite of features that are easy to manage for communication teams without any programming knowledge.

The Qabana web development team set up the website structure according to the projects wishes and needs. These were discussed in regular meetings with LUMC and EMPIRICA. After the initial website set-up, Qabana added EMPIRICA's Label2Enable team as authorised editors to the Statamic workspace, allowing them to populate the website with content. Nevertheless, Qabana will be available for technical troubleshooting regarding the website throughout the project.

Figure 2. View of the Content Management System for the Label2Enable Website

The website's interface has been tested extensively by EMPIRICA in the most popular internet browsers (Google Chrome, Ecosia, Microsoft Edge, Mozilla Firefox, Opera, Safari) – on desktop PCs and on smartphones based on Android and iOS.

2.5 Structure and contents

On launch day, the website represents the status quo at stage 1 of 2 of the project, with a structure emphasising the project presentation, regular work updates and the newsletter sign-up.

2.5.1 Default elements

As a default, each page of the website features a header, a footer and a lateral button directing to the newsletter sign-up form.

⁴ <https://statamic.com/>

Figure 3. Header with project logo, menu and search window

The header features the official project logo on the left. In the centre, the main menu displays the buttons “News”, “About”, “Participate” and “Partners”. The menu item “About” displays the sub-items “About CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2”, “About Label2Enable”, “About the Digital Single Market Strategy” and “About the European Health Data Space”. The navigation item “Engage” splits up into “Subscribe”, “Join Events” and “Comment on personas”. The right corner next to the menu features the search bar.

The footer features the project logo on the left hand. Below it, the EU funding information is displayed. The main menu is repeated in the centre, which also features a contact email address and a privacy disclaimer. On the right hand, social media buttons invite the website visitor to follow the project on LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook.

Figure 4. Footer with project and EU logo, main menu, contact details, privacy disclaimer and social media accounts

The “Subscribe” button features the question “Want to stay up to date?” with a link to the newsletter sign-up page.

Figure 5. Subscribe button with link to newsletter sign-up page

2.5.2 Landing page

The website’s landing page is divided between a header, welcome message, blocks on news and events, a Twitter feed and a footer. The welcome message captures the core concept of the project in a short paragraph, inviting visitors to read more. An impression image of the label is displayed beside it.

Figure 6. Welcome message (landing page)

Below the welcome text, the “Subscribe” button is displayed, above a Twitter feed, featuring the most recent tweets by the project’s account.

Below it, the news block displays a preview of the three most recent news items.

Beneath, a horizontal block introduces the four quality aspects of CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2. On the left, four squares with icons represent one aspect each. On the right, a text box displays general information on the quality aspects at first view and specific information on the respective aspects when hovering over the individual squares. The figure below shows the block, displaying information for “Healthy and safe”.

Figure 7. Quality aspects presentation block with alternating text box (landing page)

In the section below, a preview of upcoming events with Label2Enable’s participation is displayed.

Figure 8. Events block with latest upcoming events

The page closes with the footer.

2.5.3 News

The news page lists the project updates in chronological order. At website launch, it already featured news items on the project start, kick-off meeting, social media presence and feedback the project has provided on the adoption of the European Commission’s European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation⁵.

2.5.4 About

The “About” section contains detailed information on CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2, the project, the Digital Single Market strategy and the European Health Data Space. The first two information blocks consist of accordions, that answer different questions on the Technical Specification and the project. The latter two contain an official infographic and a short explanation on the respective EU policies.

Figure 9. About CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2 and About Label2Enable pages

2.5.5 Engage

The “Engage” section contains opportunities to subscribe the newsletter, join events and comment on the Label2Enable personas.

The “Subscribe” page contains a form to subscribe Label2Enables newsletter. Subscribe buttons directing to this page are positioned on each sub-page of the website.

⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/12663-Digital-health-data-and-services-the-European-health-data-space/F3330872_en

Subscribe

Label2Enable engages with all stakeholders interested in the topic of using CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2 and the related trusted EU mHealth label for a single market that enables patients, citizens, health professionals, systems and authorities to benefit from a healthy supply of useful apps.

To stay tuned, please fill in the form below. Label2Enable may contact you to inform you about project developments, invited you to relevant events, ask you to provide expert opinion via surveys and interviews, etc.

Email address *

First name

Last name

Organisation / Affiliation

Country

Stakeholder type

Other stakeholder type

If you like, please share with us what you are most interested in learning from the project, or what you believe you can contribute.

Terms and agreements *

I've Read And Agree With The [Terms And Agreements](#)

CANCEL SEND

Figure 10. Subscribe page

The “Events” page will only promote events under the framework of the project or with participation from Label2Enable partners.

Another engagement page invites website visitors to “Comment on personas”. The section contains the draft personas for five stakeholder groups: patients, citizens, carers; health app manufacturers; health care providers, health professionals and health professional organisations; health care systems and authorities as well as app assessment organisations or libraries. Under each draft persona, a button invites visitors to comment on the draft. Each button links to the leader of the project work package in charge of representing the respective stakeholder group (e.g., European Patients’ Forum for patients, citizens, carers).

2.5.6 Partners

The “Partners” section presents all consortium members. The page features an accordion with all partner names, whose sections each open up to display more text, as well as a full description when clicked on.

Figure 11. Partner overview page

2.6 Maintenance and evolution

Through Statamic, EMPIRICA creates and modifies the website's content according to the project's progress. The sitemap evolves, reflecting Label2Enable's work in the content-based work packages.

The initial version launched in September 2022 is mainly focussed on content presenting Label2Enable and CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2. More content on the project's specific activities will be updated as the work progresses.

Content will be presented mainly in the form of visuals and texts. The sections with most expected updates will be the "News" and "Events" section, which will both reflect ongoing project activities, as well as new sections such as "Results" which will present key outcomes of relevant project activities, accepted public deliverables, and other relevant achievements of project partners within the context of Label2Enable. Another consideration is for a glossary of health app terms to be added to the website, based on ongoing work in work package 2, to be continuously updated with new relevant terms throughout the project.

3 Project presentation slide deck

The work package 6 team has elaborated a project presentation slide deck in PowerPoint form. It is meant to be used by project partners in their own presentations as part of events and other opportunities they have to present the project. The slides can be used both as a standalone deck, as well as integrated into partners' own slides for a given opportunity. The deck contains the most important information on Label2Enable and CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2, mirroring the content in the brochure and website. The slide deck prominently refers to the website and the project's social media accounts, encouraging following and newsletter sign-up.

LABEL2 ENABLE **Key facts**

- **Title:** Adopting CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2 and a trusted EU mHealth label for a single market that enables patients, citizens, health professionals, systems and authorities to benefit from a healthy supply of useful apps.
- **Duration:** June 2022 – May 2024
- **Instrument:** Horizon Europe
- **Type:** Coordination and Support Action
- **Grant Agreement number:** 101057522
- **Budget:** 1,999.957.50 EUR
- **Partners:**

 Funded by the European Union
 9/21/22
 Title presentation
 2

Figure 12. Slide deck – slide “Key facts”

The presentation starts out with a brief description of the project by stating key project facts such as title, duration, partners involved, and budget. Then the problem space is presented, explaining the need for the project. It is based on the premise that “choosing a good health app is difficult” and this claim is supported with statistical figures from related studies.

LABEL2 ENABLE **Choosing a 'good' health app is difficult**

The sheer number of health apps makes choosing them confusing	37%
I am not sure health apps will help me	32%
I prefer face-to-face consultations with doctor/nurse	31%
I know of no health apps relevant to me	30%
I am suspicious of health apps, because I don't know who makes them	27%

Get-ehealth.eu (2015) What do patients and carers need in health apps – but are not getting? Global survey of 1,120 patients and carers

 Funded by the European Union
 9/21/22
 Title presentation
 3

Figure 13. Slide deck – slide “Choosing a “good” health app is difficult”

Before diving into the details of the project, a brief overview of the “EU Policy context” is presented which describes how the EU has been moving towards a transparent assessment of digital health apps and eventually working on promoting the wider adoption of CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2:2021 via Label2Enable.

Moving on to the project details, first the objectives are presented, along with how they are intended to be realised under “Main Areas of Work”. The latter are classified under the categories pertaining to the respective purpose they fulfil, for example whether a task helps build trust or increase use of the project, or improve adoption.

In addition, the individuals that are going to benefit from CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2:2021 have been listed along with how exactly it can help consumers make a choice i.e., by being comprehensive and inclusive.

LABEL2 ENABLE **Project pillars: trust, use and adoption**

Figure 14. Slide deck – slide “Project pillars: trust, use and adoption”

In the end, a flow chart depicts how the project promotes the health app label based on pillars of “trust, use and adoption”. The slide deck ends with contact information of the label along with a picture of team members who are working on the project.

4 Project brochure

The project brochure is designed to be used both in print and as an online version. It is in A5 format and comprises 8 individual pages (online view) or 4 A4 pages (print view). It is addressed to an interested, but not exclusively expert audience, using lay language as much as possible.

Figure 15. Project brochure cover and end page (print version)

Regarding content, the brochure aims at complementing rather than replicating the website, aiming at directing community traffic to the page, as well as to the project's social media.

The brochure is aimed to be disseminated on the website and on social media in PDF format. Ad hoc printed versions can be created for offline communication, especially during relevant events.

The content of the brochure can be primarily divided into three parts.

The first part recounts the current state of health and wellness apps in the digital world. It explains how digital health apps empower citizens to make better choices when it comes to a healthy lifestyle, and help patients navigate their treatment plan with the health professionals in a more efficient way. These apps are not only part of disease and health management but could also help prevent disease by introducing a digital approach towards developing a healthy lifestyle. But despite the practicality of these apps, identifying good apps from ineffective, unreliable, and unsecure apps is presented as a problem. Main milestones in the EU towards addressing that problem are then given, including a positioning of the Label2Enable project within that EU context.

There are many health apps ...

HEALTH APPS CAN OFFER VARIOUS BENEFITS
The use of health and wellness apps (mobile Health or mHealth, medical devices and those that are not) can empower citizens and benefit patients and carers. Health apps can for example inform them about healthy habits and choices and thus prevent or postpone chronic illnesses, help manage their disease, facilitate personalised treatment, enable better communication with health professionals, and more. On a system level, health apps can make health care more accessible, efficient and sustainable. Health apps are also welcome in the context of a shortage of health care staff, a pandemic and increasing health care costs.

OVER 350,000 HEALTH APPS
Over 350,000 consumer health apps exist worldwide. In 2020 alone, more than 90,000 such apps were introduced – an average of more than 250 apps per day. Rather than wellness management, apps increasingly focus on health condition management: 47% of all apps in 2020, up from 28% in 2015.¹

... but picking “good” health apps is difficult

HEALTH APPS DIFFER IN QUALITY AND RELIABILITY
Scientific evaluation of effectiveness and safety of mHealth has not kept pace with the growing commercial health app market. Some apps have a positive, others a negative effect on health, safety or data security. Yet, it is hard to impossible to identify the good ones in app stores or online.² To enable more informed decisions several authorities, private and public organisations have created health app assessment frameworks. However, most of them provide assessment results of no more than a few dozen apps. “The WHO compared in 2018 20 health app assessment frameworks for the EU.³ The frameworks differed a lot in topics covered, stakeholders addressed, existing frameworks referenced, and standards aligned with. A recent Nature article that compared health app policies in nine countries concluded none of them had yet succeeded in making health app assessment processes efficient.⁴ This multitude of frameworks creates an unworkable situation for app manufacturers and proves counterproductive in achieving trust, uptake and funding of health apps. Currently, the potential of health apps in sustaining health care budgets, improving quality and accessibility of health care and addressing the shortage in health care staff is heavily underutilised.

European Union policy context

THE EU’S STEPS TOWARDS A COMMON TRANSPARENT ASSESSMENT OF HEALTH APPS

- The *Green Paper on mobile health* (2014)⁵ addresses the potential benefits and risks of health apps questioning **how to verify or ensure the efficacy of health apps (e.g. certification schemes) and how to better inform end users** on the quality and safety of health apps.
- The *Communication on enabling the digital transformation of health and care in the Digital Single Market* (2018)⁶ highlights digital tools and data for citizen empowerment and person-centred care as a key priority and proposes **common principles and certification** to facilitate supply of these tools also by Small and Medium-sized Enterprises.
- The *Proposal for a Regulation on the European Health Data Space (2022)*⁷ calls for a **voluntary labelling system for wellness apps** (Article 31) and a **casading effect in medical devices** that aim to be interoperable with Electronic Health Record systems.

Figure 16. Brochure pages focusing on introducing the problem space and the EU progress

The second part introduces CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2:2021, the assessment framework, EU certification scheme, the health app quality label and report.

WHAT IS CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2:2021?

A TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION TO HELP YOU IDENTIFY QUALITY HEALTH APPS
CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2:2021 *Health software – Part 2: Health and wellness apps – Quality and reliability*⁸ was an assignment by the European Commission to the European Committee for Standardization (CEN). The initiative went global in its cooperation with the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC). CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2 was published in July 2021. The Technical Specification offers a **health app quality assessment framework** and a **health app quality label**, inspired by the very effective EU energy label.

HOW DOES CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2:2021 WORK?

HEALTH APP QUALITY ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORK AND EU CERTIFICATION SCHEME
The CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2 health app quality assessment framework consists of 81 questions. Sixty-seven of these questions are score-impacting quality requirement questions. The framework was grounded in 25 existing frameworks, a Delphi study with 83 experts from eight stakeholder groups from six continents and tested for the Dutch Ministry of Health with COVID-19 symptom apps. The framework refers to 28 existing standards.

To obtain the health app quality label for a specific app, manufacturers must provide supporting evidence. This evidence will be assessed by a CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2 accredited app assessment organisation using the EU certification scheme (“handbook for accredited app assessors”) that Label2Enable will develop.

HEALTH APP QUALITY LABEL AND REPORT
The health app quality label communicates the results of the CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2 health app assessment in one glance. It displays characteristics like name, icon, manufacturer and health benefit of the app as well as scores, ranging from a green A (best score) to a red E (worst score) in four quality aspects. After testing with people with limited health literacy these aspects were phrased:

- **Healthy and safe**
- **Easy to use**
- **Secure data**
- **Robust build**

Label2Enable will translate the label in all the official commonly used European languages.

The health app quality report reveals the answers to all 81 questions of the framework in the level of detail health professionals need to recommend a health app and insurers need as a basis for reimbursement decision-making. Label2Enable will gather guidance what that level of detail is.

What is a Technical Specification?
A Technical Specification (TS) is work still under technical development. A TS is published for immediate use, but it is also a means to obtain feedback. The aim is that it will eventually be transformed and republished as an International Standard (IS).

Health app quality label and report structure:

- Flag or logo: Health app quality label
- App icon: App name
- Platform icons
- Name app manufacturer
- Benefit of the app: With this app [intended users] can [intended use] / With this app [in 10] [intended users] [health effect] [if use]. Check [here] when app requires approval from a health professional before use.
- Healthy and safe: B A
- Easy to use: D C B A
- Secure data: E D C B A
- Robust build: A
- Overall health app quality score: C B A
- App checked on [date]

CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2:2021

Figure 17. Brochure pages focusing on explaining the TS, the label and the associated report

The third part of the brochure introduces the main stakeholders who can benefit from the CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2:2021. It also provides a high-level overview of key actions that the project is planned to take, grouped into the categories trust, use and adoption.

WHO CAN BENEFIT FROM CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2:2021?

For example:

- Patients, citizens, and carers who seek to use health apps
- App manufacturers who seek to deliver quality apps
- Health care providers, health professionals and health professional organisations who seek to recommend or prescribe apps
- Health and care systems and authorities who seek to reimburse apps
- App assessment organisations who seek to use a trusted, globally recognised health app assessment framework
- App stores and app libraries who seek to help their customers make informed decisions on health apps

WHAT DOES THE LABEL2ENABLE PROJECT DO?

LABEL2ENABLE HELPS IMPLEMENT CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2:2021
Label2Enable is built on three pillars:

TRUST
Trust adds the missing trust elements that stakeholders require to use the label and adopt the TS. Label2Enable will co-create an EU certification scheme ('handbook for accredited app assessors') aligned with EU values and EU legislation (General Data Protection Regulation, Medical Device Regulation etc.). The certification scheme will be tested with six health app assessment organisations, including two notified bodies, and 24 health app manufacturers. An entity will be set up to maintain the EU certification scheme and have app assessors accredited. And the project will evaluate different business models for app assessment and explore existing label legislations to assess their applicability to the health app quality label.

USE
Label2Enable will co-create the communication consumers and health professionals need to consider to download and use and to recommend health apps. An intentionally diverse patient, citizen, and carer advisory group and health professional advisory group are set up to ensure the citizen and health professional centredness of project tasks. A survey for citizens and one for health professionals will explore which types of health apps are already recommended and used, thoughts on reviewing, rating and recommending apps, added value of the label, and which remaining barriers to address. We test the label in four corners of Europe with people with low health literacy to learn how to introduce the label, find out how to effectively display the label in app stores, app libraries and trusted health sources, and provide guidance on the content of the health app quality report.

ADOPTION
Trust and use promote adoption of the assessment framework and the label by health care systems and authorities, as well as app stores, app libraries and other trusted sources. Label2Enable aims to co-create a single market for health apps (cross-country recognition of the EU certification scheme). We will support health care systems and authorities in piloting CEN-ISO/TS 82304-2 and document these pilots in 'use stories'. With health insurers and Health Technology Assessment (HTA) bodies we will explore the potential of the TS in decision-making on reimbursement. We engage with stakeholders in many ways. Also to look five to ten years ahead what success of the TS would be to them and how to get there.

Figure 18. Brochure pages focusing on the main stakeholders and main project activities

Finally, the brochure ends with an invitation to sign up for the project newsletter and gives the contact information for the project's website and all the social media channels.

5 Promotion and dissemination outlook

This section outlines further promotion and dissemination plans, which will be presented in more detail in D6.2.

5.1 Virtual Communication Office Team

EMPIRICA is coordinating promotion, communication and dissemination efforts in a virtual Communication Office Team (vCOT). The team is staffed with one representative per partner organisation and meets once monthly. It coordinates efforts, identifies communication and dissemination opportunities and takes stock of completed dissemination activities.

Table 1. Member list of the virtual Communication Office Team

Member of the VCOT	Consortium Partner	Role
Petra Hoogendoorn	Leiden University Medical Center	Project coordinator
Cynthia Hallensleben	National eHealth Living Lab	Communication manager
Tom de Vree	i~HD	T1.3 task leader
Rachel Fuller	ORCHA	WP3 leader
Estefania Cordero	European Patients' Forum	Communication manager
Strahil Birov	EMPIRICA	WP6 lead
Carola Schulz	EMPIRICA	WP6 team manager
Barbara Pes	COCIR	Communication manager
Marianna Imenokhoeva	HIMSS	Communication manager
Sari Makkonen	EIT Health	Communication manager
Corine Meppelink	UvA	Communication manager
Julia van Weert	UvA	T4.4 task leader
Caoimhe Kelly	EuroHealthNet	Communication manager
Vania Putatti	EuroHealthNet	T4.3 task leader
Victor Barbera	TIC Salut	Communication manager
Ana Belen	TIC Salut	Communication manager
Tatjana Trupec	OptimIT	T7.2 task leader
Giuseppe D'Avenio	Italian National Institute of Health	Communication manager
Ieva Tamulyte	Kauno Klinikos	Communication manager

5.2 Social media

Other important tools of Label2Enable promotion and dissemination are the project's social media accounts. While D6.2 will outline a detailed social media strategy with dedicated Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), this chapter summarises the efforts made so far and the future work envisioned.

To address different audiences, Label2Enable is present on three different platforms.

Table 2. Overview of Label2Enable social media platforms

Platform	Account Name	URL	Followers as of 16 September 2022
Twitter	@Label2E	https://twitter.com/Label2E	178
LinkedIn	Label2Enable	https://www.linkedin.com/company/label2enable	263
Facebook	@Label2Enable	https://www.facebook.com/Label2Enable/	15

The communications team has ensured that each partner is following these accounts on the platforms that are relevant to digital health apps and digital health in general, in order to create a valuable community. More specifically, the team has targeted organisations and individuals representing the stakeholder groups at the core of the project (see section 2.1). The communication strategy entails not only regular publishing of relevant content, but also engagement with other parties' publications, to create an interactive community.

The vCOT ensures that the project partners align their social media publishing activities with the overall project communication strategy. This entails referencing to the project's posts, mutual following on all platforms, strategic tagging of accounts and use of the hashtag #Label2Enable across all platforms, which is used for analytics reporting. Also, the social media strategy aims at creating a relevant community that represents and reaches the stakeholder groups targeted in the project and brings them together in constructive dialogue. A starting point is the follower community of the consortium partners, which amounts to over 320,000 followers on Twitter alone.

The first joint coordinated communication effort the consortium put into action on social media was the campaign accompanying the website launch. WP6 lead empirica created a series of posts and visuals (including alternative texts) to disseminate the project website launch on LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook. These were distributed to all consortium members and posted according to an editorial schedule. The screenshots below show some of the successful posts.

Figure 19. Website launch social media posts

Figure 20. Facebook wallpaper promoting the website launch

In the week following the website launch, on Twitter alone a total of 20 Tweets used the hashtag #Label2Enable, published by 16 contributors and generating 173,197 impressions.⁶

While the social media KPIs will be outlined in detail in D6.2, the table below lists the figures WP6 intends to monitor:

Platform	Performance Indicator	Comment
ALL	No of posts/ tweets using the hashtag #Label2Enable	Tracking across all accounts; for each platform separately
ALL	No of accounts using the hashtag #Label2Enable	Tracking across all accounts; for each platform separately
ALL	No of followers of the project’s accounts	Tracking of the project’s accounts; for each platform separately
ALL	No of posts/tweets by the project’s accounts	Tracking of the project’s accounts; for each platform separately
ALL	No of post/tweet impressions of posts by the project’s accounts	Tracking of the project’s accounts; for each platform separately
ALL	Post engagement rate for posts by the project’s accounts	Tracking of the project’s accounts; for each platform separately
ALL	No of post engagements	Tracking of the project’s accounts; for each platform separately
ALL	No of social media campaigns	Number of coordinated communication campaigns on social media

⁶ Source: trackmyhashtag.com, searching for #Label2Enable, 07. September – 15. September

5.3 Dissemination

WP6 maintains a dissemination effort table to keep track of upcoming dissemination opportunities and record past efforts. The table records the following information:

- ▶ Upcoming events suitable for project dissemination: future events on mHealth and digital health that could be used for presenting Label2Enable or for networking with the relevant stakeholder groups;
- ▶ Reported past stakeholder engagement activities: past events, publications or social media activities promoting Label2Enable;
- ▶ Ideas for future stakeholder engagement: unstructured possibilities for stakeholder engagement – such as podcasts etc.;
- ▶ Publications: past publications (reports, papers, grey literature, etc.) mentioning Label2Enable.

All partners have access to the file in the project's SharePoint and are encouraged to contribute to it. WP6 leaders use the monthly vCOT, consortium meetings and further opportunities to update the table with unput from other work packages.

All engagement efforts are categorised according to type of stakeholders reached and perceived impact.

The first major dissemination effort of the project related to Label2Enable's feedback to the European Health Data Space Regulation Proposal in late July 2022, which was promoted on LinkedIn and Twitter, as well as posted on the website.

Concrete dissemination contents will follow as the project work advances – such as a scientific article on the patient, citizen and carer survey (T4.2 – M8) and a survey for healthcare professionals (T5.2 – M8), a white paper on evaluation of label legislations (T2.3 – M12), a scientific article on Business Model Assessment (T3.3 – M15) or a health app quality report (T5.3 – M24), to name a few.

Figure 21. Dissemination of Label2Enable feedback on EHDS on LinkedIn